

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 5.4

3rd Annual CYCLOPES Community Building Report

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1. Summary

One of the main goals of the CYCLOPES project is to build, strengthen and maintain links with initiatives, actions, and projects relevant to CYCLOPES, learning and developing from the collective efforts, where possible. Continuing from the foundation laid in the 1st Annual CYCLOPES Community Building Report (D5.2), the CYCLOPES consortium went from the phase of being visible and open to the phase where a more active approach towards community building has been central. The partners of the CYCLOPES consortium have used their available means to reach end users from LEAs, relevant stakeholders, academia and industry.

This report D5.4 “3rd Annual CYCLOPES Community Building Report” describes the main results achieved from May 2023 to April 2024.

2. Introduction

A broad and active community is essential in building an open network for European experienced practitioners’ working in the field of fighting cybercrime. However, there are already many institutions, networks and other initiatives focused on these domains that are relevant for the CYCLOPES project.

Aside from the internal LEA community, CYCLOPES forms a bridge between the project and: 1) EU and international organisations, such as EC, EC3, Europol’s Innovation Hub, Interpol, ENISA, etc. 2) Networks of practitioners, especially ENLETS, ENFSI, i-LEAD, iLeaNet, EU-HYBNET and i-ProcureNet 3) networks and relevant stakeholders related to cybersecurity 4) research, industry, ethical and social societies and organisations.

In the first year of the project implementation, the methodology was developed as a starting point for establishing relations with the relevant stakeholders. The CYCLOPES Community Building Framework and Governance model (D5.1) defined the methodology, by which over the course of this 5-year-project, all members of the CYCLOPES community work together to reach the goals, ambition and granted objectives of the project.

3. Overview of main achievements: 3rd year (May 2023 – April 2024)

During the first year, most actions have evolved around gaining awareness and visibility; the second year, focused on the implementation, the team invited and motivated practitioners and other stakeholders to have a more practical hands-on experience with the CYCLOPES activities. In the third year, all activities focused on community building and establishing links were continued.

The project builds, strengthens and maintains links with the key stakeholders and networks indicated in the graphic, whose work is conducted in the areas relevant to CYCLOPES:

Figure 1 Cooperation with other relevant stakeholders

The cooperation with the networks and stakeholders named above is foreseen through exchanging information about the ongoing and planned activities, particularly workshops, surveys/questionnaires, conferences, etc. The exchange of selected reports and other project outcomes, relevant for both parties and the synchronisation of conducted actions, should help avoid duplicating and overlapping work.

3.1. Key stakeholders

The project has ongoing communication and exchange of information about events and ongoing activities with the following key stakeholders:

- a. European Commission, DG HOME (D.4. Security in the digital age). The Commission's Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs is responsible for the EU's internal security policy, which is a component of the new Security Union Strategy 2020-2025. The aim is to build a safer Europe by fighting terrorism and organised crime by promoting police cooperation and by preparing to swiftly respond to emerging crises. DG HOME actions in this area include stricter rules against illicit trafficking of firearms and on trafficking in human beings, as well as revision of legislation on combating child sexual abuse, sexual exploitation and child pornography.¹
- b. European Union Agency for Criminal Justice Cooperation (EJCN). EJCN was established to foster contacts between practitioners specialised in countering the challenges posed by cybercrime, cyber-enabled crime and investigations in cyberspace, and to increase the efficiency of investigations and prosecutions. The EJCN facilitates and enhances cooperation between competent judicial authorities by enabling the exchange of expertise, best practice and other relevant knowledge regarding the investigation and prosecution of cybercrime.²

¹ https://commission.europa.eu/about-european-commission/departments-and-executive-agencies/migration-and-home-affairs_en.

² <https://www.eurojust.europa.eu>.

- c. European Anti-Cybercrime Technology Development Association (EACTDA). The purpose of the Association is the development of technological solutions for European Law Enforcement Agencies and Forensic Laboratories for their fight against crime.³
- d. European Cybercrime Training and Education Group (ECTEG). ECTEG is composed of European Union and European Economic Area Member States law enforcement agencies, international bodies, academia, private industry and experts. The primary aim of the working group is to provide experience and knowledge to further enhance the coordination of cybercrime training, by identifying opportunities to build the capacity of countries to combat cybercrime through the development and delivery of a robust and enduring training programme.⁴
- e. European Network of Forensic Science Institutes (ENFSI). ENFSI was founded with the purpose of improving the mutual exchange of information in the field of forensic science. This, as well as improving the quality of forensic science delivery in Europe, has become the main issue of the network. Besides the general work in the fields of quality and competence management, research and development and education and training, different forensic expertizes are dealt with by 17 different expert working groups.⁵
- f. European Network of Law Enforcement Technology Services (ENLETS). In ENLETS 29 members from across Europe are brought together to address and action shared priorities. ENLETS enables the sharing of best practices on a broad level, engaging on mutual priorities and stimulating future projects that can help fill the gaps and the known issues facing law enforcement of its members. The environment promotes collaboration and fosters a supportive network, working to help each other through current challenges.⁶
- g. EUROPOL Innovation Lab. The Lab aims to identify, promote and develop concrete innovative solutions in support of the EU Member States' operational work. This will help investigators and analysts to make the most of the opportunities offered by new technologies to avoid duplication of work, create synergies and pool resources.⁷

Moreover, in the third year of the project implementation, a cooperation with INTERPOL and CEPOL has been initiated.

- h. International Criminal Police Organization (INTERPOL). INTERPOL is an international organization that facilitates police cooperation and provides investigative support, expertise and training to law enforcement worldwide, focusing on three major areas of transnational crime: terrorism, cybercrime and organized crime.⁸
- i. EU Agency for Law Enforcement Training (CEPOL). CEPOL is an agency of the European Union that builds a network of training institutes for law enforcement officials in EU Member States and supports them in providing frontline training on security

³ <https://www.eactda.eu/index.html>

⁴ <https://www.ecteg.eu/>

⁵ <https://enfsi.eu/>

⁶ <https://enlets.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.europol.europa.eu/operations-services-and-innovation/innovation-lab>

⁸ <https://www.interpol.int/en>

priorities, law enforcement cooperation and information exchange. CEPOL also works with EU bodies, international organizations and third countries to ensure that the most serious security threats are tackled with a collective response. The agency's annual work programme is built with the input from this network and other stakeholders, resulting in topical and focused activities designed to meet the needs of Member States in the priority areas of the EUs internal security strategy. Moreover, CEPOL assesses training needs to address EU security priorities. CEPOL constantly strives to offer innovative and advanced training activities by integrating relevant developments in knowledge, research and technology and by creating synergies through strengthened cooperation.⁹

3.2. CYCLOPES Community Members

One of the CYCLOPES' key goals is to build and maintain an innovation-driven network of European law enforcement agencies and experts specialised in combating cybercrime. Different techniques and platforms are commonly used to engage with the CYCLOPES communities - some of them are designed specifically to share information, while others aim to successfully involve practitioners, industry and researchers in relevant activities'.

It is possible to join the CYCLOPES Community after signing up on <https://cyclopes-project.eu>, (via click on JOIN US button). This page provides a snapshot of the project and what members can expect from the support of the initiative. At the beginning of the project, CYCLOPES created a list of Community Members, which is stored on the project repository and increases during the course of the project. There are currently around 230 practitioners involved, who work in the field of fighting cybercrime.

Figure 2 CYCLOPES network geographical regions

Specific members of the CYCLOPES community are involved in the project activities through participation in the practitioners' workshops, annual dissemination workshops, webinars and

⁹ <https://www.cepola.europa.eu/>

other relevant activities. Moreover, CYCLOPES is in continuous contact with all community members to synchronise and to define the CYCLOPES priority topics for the following years.

3.3. CYCLOPES Community building activities'

The CYCLOPES team has dedicated efforts to enlarge the community and attends various events and meetings across Europe, helping to build connections and working partnerships with relevant stakeholders and other projects.

1. WP Leaders meeting with CEPOL on 20th - 21st June 2023 in Budapest.
2. Tools4LEAs Event on 28th June 2023 in Paris.
3. UNCOVER Summer School and Capture the Flag (CTF) Event on 4th – 8th September 2023 in Prague.
4. EU Innovation Hub meeting on 4th October 2023 in Brussels.
5. 15th Forensic Technology Days on 26th and 27th September 2023 in Germany.
6. European Anti-Cybercrime Technology Development Association (EACTDA) meeting on 13th – 14th March 2024 in Lisbon.
7. European Clearing Board meeting on 10th and 11th April 2024 in Brussels.
8. Security and Policing Event 2024 on 12th – 14th March 2024 in UK.
9. Conference 'The Hybrid World of Cybersecurity' on 10th – 11th April 2024 in Athens.

In addition, to stimulate the dialogue on pressing security matters and crime issues, the CYCLOPES project organized several events within *WP6 Communication and dissemination activities*, which are closely linked to community building:

1. 2nd Dissemination Event, that was held online on 21st September 2023. The event was designed for the CYCLOPES Community - 99 people registered for the event, and the final audience consisted of 74 participants from LEAs across Europe, industry and science as well as relevant networks and organizations responsible for fighting cybercrime. The aim of this event was to disseminate the CYCLOPES project findings to a large spectrum of stakeholders and ensure efficient interaction with relevant partners who may join the CYCLOPES network and its activities. Participants had an opportunity to learn at a glance about the recent network activities and raise awareness of the CYCLOPES project.
2. 2nd CYCLOPES webinar, organized in collaboration with European Judicial Cybercrime Network (EJCN), was held online on 7th December 2023. The subject of 2nd webinar 'Enterprises as a Victims of Cybercrime' covered the various legal and practical aspects of remediation for victims and similar cases of cybercrime. This time, the webinar was dedicated only for the CYCLOPES Consortium, Law Enforcement Agencies, prosecutors, and judicial experts from the EJCN, specialized in countering the challenges of cybercrime and cyber-enabled crime. The CYCLOPES project also connects and builds synergies between Member State LEAs, industry and academia partners by stimulating and sustaining dialogue on pressing European cyber security matters. Therefore, we realized that it would be valuable to focus on companies and protection of their rights as a victim of crime in national prosecution procedures and operational challenges in this area.
3. 3rd Dissemination Event held on 16th – 17th April in Vienna. This networking event brought together representatives of European Commission, other relevant organizations and members of law enforcement agencies to discuss various topics that support the successful fight against cybercrime and prevent cybercrime. In addition, the event aims to share experiences and present the outcomes of

different European projects and initiatives, which are working in the field of fighting cybercrime (Anti-FinTer, CYBERSPACE, POLIICE, UnderServed, NOTIONES, EU-HYBNET, ENACT, FORMOBILE, STARLIGHT, ALIGNER, Decrypt Square, Emerge IoT, UNCOVER, TCO Cluster (ALLIES, FRISCO, TATE), MISP-LEA, AIL, eFirst, Overclock, ARICA, LEAGUE, CPORT).

3.4. ENLETS Messenger Service (EMS)

Part of the community building activities is focused on cooperation with the use of communication and collaboration platforms developed or used in other networks. This provides an ideal opportunity to exploit the efforts of these initiatives and to spend time on establishing links and building relations, rather than the considerable time and resources required to develop such communication channels.

ENLETS has offered a dedicated space for the CYCLOPES Community on their ENLETS Messenger Service (EMS), where practitioners can chat, collaborate on work-related topics and establish relations. This solution provides a safe, encrypted chat experience through a dedicated mobile application and web browser service. CYCLOPES currently use a dedicated channel for internal communication as well as ENLETS provides a 'general' channel for sharing information about the upcoming events and relevant outcomes.

4. Upcoming and planned community building activities

In the coming months of the implementation, the project will continue the collaboration with key stakeholders as well as research projects and other initiatives in the area of fighting cybercrime. To effectively manage community building, the following steps have been implemented:

Figure 3 Community building plan

To achieve the results, a dedicated electronic template has been created to collect all relevant projects and initiatives on cybercrime that might be of interest to the CYCLOPES project as well as establish connections. This process is flexible and adapted to the current needs.

5. Conclusion

This document described how the building up of the CYCLOPES Community is managed and summarized the results achieved in the period from May 2023 to April 2024. This report may also have informative value for other stakeholders to build greater awareness of the planned CYCLOPES activities and foster synergies.

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